

EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT TESTING CONDITIONS ON TENSILE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER YARN

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Key words: carbon fiber, yarn, tensile properties, testing conditions

ABSTRACT

Particular care has been always taken in the carbon fiber/resin composites, and the most critical parameters for engineering application are tensile strength and tensile modulus. ASTM D4018–11, JIS R7608-2007 and ISO 10618-2004 have shown a set of detailed instructions for tensile testing of resin-impregnated yarn. However, some problems still exist that the different sample preparation and testing conditions can generate a certain number of discrete data causing a great barrier to compare the results during my experiments. In this paper, the effects of different sample preparation and testing conditions on tensile properties of carbon fiber yarn, including T300B-3K, T700SC-12K and T800HB-6K supplied by Toray, have been investigated systematically based on types of resin and resin contents of impregnated yarn and tensile speeds. Thus the appropriate determination parameters for impregnated yarn have been got. The results showed that resin with high mechanical properties, good wettability, and low viscosity in room temperature could be employed, and the resin content of impregnated yarn should be controlled more than 30%. Furthermore, we suggest that tensile speed of 2mm/min and 5mm/min is suitable for the determination of tensile properties of impregnated yarn. As for the determination of modulus, strain range between 0.3% and 0.6% could be adopted for setting the strain parameters of extensometer.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since Thomas Edison carbonized cotton threads or bamboo slivers into an all-carbon fiber for the first time at high temperatures as a filament of the incandescent light bulb [1], high-performance carbon fiber with higher tensile strength and modulus entered the global markets gradually. In present, more and more carbon fiber companies are established on a global scale. The most famous carbon fiber companies are Toray and Hexcel. There are three series of carbon fiber in HEXEL and they are AS series like AS4C, AS4 and AS4D, IM series like IM4, IM6, IM7, IM8, IM9 and \HM series of high modulus graphite fibers. In Toray, two series that T and M series are mainly produce, whose strength varies from 3500MPa to 6300MPa and modulus from 230GPa to 600GPa. In China, some companies also joined the manufacturing of carbon fiber several years ago, which have certain capacity to manufacture

high-performance carbon fiber, such as Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co., Hengshen Co. Thus in order to achieve engineering application, the determination of tensile strength and tensile modulus would be very critical.

With the further understanding of carbon fiber, tensile testing methods has experienced from the monofilament test [2,3] to loose-bundle tensile test [4-6] and subsequently impregnated yarn tensile test [4]. Even though Tensile strength obtained from single fiber tensile testing which is more time-consuming is recommend by more than 30 monofilaments for test, this method does not represent the fiber mechanical behavior in tow significantly due to the size effects of different single fibers. And loose-bundle tensile tests are greatly influenced by the sample preparation process, which are pretty difficult to ensure that each fiber in the bundle is vertical and no damage and determine tensile modulus caused by setting the extensometer uneasily. So carbon fiber tensile properties testing is ruled by the impregnated yarn method [7-10]. In the 1970s, the impregnated yarn tensile method of glass fibers [11-14] is applied on carbon fibers by the Union Carbide Corporation of the U.S. for the first time, which do not get the rapid spread in the ensuing decade. As improving of standards and promoting the implementation of standards by the American Association of Advanced Composite Materials Suppliers, it makes the impregnated yarn tensile method of carbon fiber to be universal and accepted by the global industries of carbon fiber for now. This test method is used to measure the true performance of carbon fiber combined with resin. However, during the experiment, we found that the different sample preparation and testing conditions can generate a certain number of discrete datum [15-17] causing a great barrier to compare the results with the different test institutions. It is pretty necessary to operate a systematic study about the tensile testing conditions and then identify effective and uniform key parameters for tensile testing based on some existing standards.

In this paper, T300B, T700SC and T800HB are employed to investigate the effects of different sample preparation and testing conditions on tensile properties of carbon fiber yarn involving types of resin and resin content of impregnated yarn and tensile speed, referring to the tensile testing standards [18,19] of carbon fiber (ASTM D4018-11, JIS R7608-2007 and ISO 10618-2004) and processes of yarn tensile tests mentioned in some related theses.. Thus the appropriate determination parameters for impregnated yarn are got based on experiment results, which are attributed to the tensile test of carbon fiber and comparison of data with different testing institution adopting the consistent determination parameters.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Raw materials

Three types of PAN-based carbon fibers (T300B-3K, T700SC-12K, T800HB-6K) were supplied from Toray Industries, Inc.. And epoxy resin LY-1 and E51(epoxy value: 0.48-0.54) were purchased from Shenyang Southeast Chemical Engineering Institute and Bluestar New Chemical Materials Co., Ltd. Wuxi Resin Factory, respectively. Triethylenetetramine (CR), methylhexahydrophthalic anhydride (CR) and polyether amine D400 (T.P.) were supplied from Xilong Chemical Co., Ltd., Shanghai Bingqi Chemical Technology Co., Ltd., and Huntsman Corp., respectively. Acetone (AR) was purchased from Qingdao Kaite Chemical Co., Ltd.

	T300B	T700SC	T800HB
Tensile strength•/MPa	3530	4900	5490
Tensile modulus•/GPa	230	230	290
Fracture elongation•/%	1.5	2.1	1.9

• represents the value from the industry.

Table 1 The basic mechanical properties of carbon fibers

2.2 Specimen preparation

Specific steps of preparing the impregnated yarn [20,21] are sequentially followed by preparation of resin mixture, fiber cut, fiber impregnated, the impregnated yarn cured and reinforcing pieces pasted. The resin, curing agent and acetone are directly mixed by a certain percentage and stirred in a homemade tank. And then yarn cut about 400mm is placed in this tank with constant tension for about 3 to 5 minutes. The impregnated yarn is removed from the tank and then fixed on a steel shelf also with constant tension after shaken off the excess resin, which should be put in a specified circumstance($23\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH}<60\%$) for about 2 hours to volatilize the acetone in the impregnated yarn. After that, these yarn are cured according to the corresponding process and subsequently cooled down to room temperature in the oven, which can avoid the introduction of any residual stresses. The final step is to cut the cured yarn at 250mm and then paste reinforcing pieces($50\text{mm}\times 20\text{mm}$) on both ends of yarn, thus causing standard samples with a efficient length of about 150mm for tensile testing. Note that as received, epoxy resin (LY-1) combined with its curing agent is defined as resin A, E51 with polyether amine D400 as resin B and E51 with triethylenetetramine as resin C.

2.3 Tensile testing

The universal mechanical testing machine (INSTRON 5967) is employed to test the tensile properties of impregnated yarn. Besides a extensometer matching INSTRON 5967 is used to obtain the tensile modulus with a span length of 50mm. It is necessary to keep a specified circumstance($23\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH}<60\%$) during tensile testing.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The fracture effectiveness of tensile specimen

Typical failure modes and locations may be grouped for the fiber. Choose, if possible, a standard description using the three-part failure mode code that is recommend in ASTM D4018-11. Through our experiments summarized, in order to ensure the effective results of tensile specimen, before testing we should choose these impregnated yarn with resin content of more than 30% and without apparent resin balls or defects as tensile specimen. It is known to all that most of impregnated yarn will collapse into many sections remaining nothing between upper and lower fixtures while testing. In such case, the

effective results of tensile specimen can be confirmed without unusual tensile curves if failure areas are not inside grip/tap or at grip/tap and failure types are not long splitting, fiber pull out or explosive [18].

Figure 1: Fracture contrast of effective and ineffective specimen. (a) effective; (b) ineffective.

The Fig.1a shows effective specimen which appear to be ideal fracture modes. As shown in Fig.1b, it can be observed that failure modes of these ineffective specimen are mainly failure at grip/tap, long splitting, fiber pull out and explosive. The effective results of tensile specimen can be obtained after removing these ineffective specimen and their testing results.

3.2 The effects of different types of resins on tensile properties of fibers

The accuracy of impregnated yarn testing is greatly influenced by the mechanical properties of resin. So it is necessary to choose a proper resin system and in this section three kind of resin systems are investigated mainly about curing degree, tensile strength, tensile modulus and fracture elongation.

The curing degree of resin system can easily be got by measuring the heat release before and after cured by the differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, METTLER Toledo Co.). In Table 2, we can clearly acquire that three kind of resin systems are almost completely cured. And ensuring resin close to be completely cured is a premise of the accuracy of impregnated yarn tensile testing.

	Resin A	Resin B	Resin C
Curing process	80°C 3h	80°C 2h, 125°C 3h	120°C 0.5h
Heat release before cured, J/g	379.35	318.16	205.16
Heat release after cured, J/g	21.31	4.80	Almost 0
Curing degree	94.38%	98.49%	100%

Table 2: Curing characteristics of three kind of resins

Three kind of resin systems are cured based on the corresponding curing process, which need to pay more attention to avoid the resin systems over-cured. The mechanical properties of resins are studied according to ASTM D638-10 (detail data and curves in Fig.2).

Figure 2: Tensile properties of neat resins. (a) Stress-strain curves. (b) Tensile strength of resins. (c) Tensile modulus of resins. (d) Fracture elongation.

The studies focusing on the mechanical properties of neat resins attribute us to analyze the effects of types of resin on the tensile properties of impregnated yarn. It can be observed that resin A and C show higher strength than 80MPa and modulus than 2.3GPa compared with resin B (Fig. 2b and 2c). In Fig. 2d, resin A and B have greater fracture elongation than 7%. As shown in Fig.2a, a great difference would take place when the loading of neat resins come to the top. The tensile curve of resin B exhibits an obvious yield phenomenon [22] and lower strength and modulus due to the long chains of the curing agent provided by polyether amine D400 reducing the crosslinking density, which make the cured resin a sparser cross-linked network and larger molecular chain space thus increasing the toughness of the resin. So during the tensile testing the resin sample appear to be a necking behavior producing a long tensile platform in that curve. In contrast, resin A has a shorter chains of the curing agent provided by methyl hexahydrophthalic anhydride than that of D400, which can present a slightly yield phenomenon but no a tensile platform. However, the tensile curve from resin C shows a little yield resulting in a brittle fracture owing to the short-chain amine curing agent employed. The resin systems suitable for the tensile testing of impregnated yarn should meet the requirements of high strength and fracture elongation.

Figure 3: The effects of different types of resins on tensile properties of carbon fibers.
(a) Tensile strength. (b) Tensile modulus

In Fig.3, it is suggested that types of resins have a strong influence on tensile properties of fiber. And resin A can ensure the accuracy of the tensile strength of three kind of carbon fibers listed in Table 1. The tensile strength of carbon fibers(T300B-3K, T800HB-6K) can be accurately determined combined with resin C, but it is difficult for T700SC-12K with resin C. However, resin B cannot be adopted to testing the tensile strength of carbon fibers. Of course, we can observe that the tensile modulus of carbon fibers has hardly influenced by selected resins.

For resin A, it can be used as the impregnated resin of carbon fibers due to its significant mechanical properties and strong interfacial interactions with carbon fibers. Also, it has a lower viscosity easily to penetrate into the interior of yarn further and a lower increasing speed of viscosity guaranteeing to infiltrate carbon fibers fully. Moreover, resin C has a great barrier to fully infiltrating the lager tows like T700SC-12K due to a higher increasing speed of viscosity. But it can be used as the impregnated resin of smaller tows carbon fibers like T300B-3K or T800HB-6K as shown in Fig3. For resin B, when combined with three kind of carbon fibers it cannot ensure the accurate tensile strength. The main reasons are the following aspects:

(1) lower mechanical properties

As shown in Fig. 2, resin B has a lower tensile strength only about 55MPa than that of resin A and C. Also, its tensile modulus is almost 10% lower compared with that of resin A and C.

(2) weaker interfacial properties

It can be seen in Fig.3a that the tensile strength of carbon fibers impregnated by resin B are lower than others. So in order to investigate whether that is caused by the interfacial compatibility, we compare the interfacial performances of T300B fiber with three kind of resins. A microbond method for determination of the interface shear strength between fibers and resin [23-27] is employed to investigate the matching behaviors of resin and fibers.

Figure 4: The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of T300B fiber with three kind of resins

According to the results of Fig. 4, the carbon fiber combined with resin A has a superior IFSS about 58MPa, and resin C which corresponds to about 64MPa. But the IFSS of resin B is only about 50% of both the front and about 34MPa. From a simple comparison of the data, it is clear that the IFSS of carbon fibers with resin B is relatively poor, which is originated from the sparser cross-linked network formed and the weak compatibility between carbon fibers and resin B. Thus curing agents with a long chain length like D400 cannot be employed for the sample preparation.

3.3 The effects of different resin contents on tensile properties of fibers

The mechanical properties of impregnated yarn depends not only on carbon fibers, but also a great relevance to the resin. Suitable resin contents can contribute to protecting the fibers during the testing process, in which fibers may be uniformly carried, hence their carrying capacities could be taken full advantage and the measurement accuracy for tensile properties of carbon fibers can be improved. In this part, resin A is chosen and different resin contents of impregnated yarn are designed to evaluate how the resin contents influence the tensile properties. Resin contents including 25%-30%, 30%-35%, 35%-40%, 40%-45% are prepared by adjusting the addition of acetone and the crafts of specimen preparation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: The effects of different resin contents on tensile properties of resin A-impregnated fibers.
(a) Tensile strength. (b) Tensile modulus

In Fig.5, the tensile strength and modulus of impregnated yarn with a resin content less than 30% have a certain deviation from the manufacturer's recommendations. They present comminuted fracture modes mainly due to the lower resin content and weaker load transfer between the resin and fiber easily generating a large area of chip damages. As for T300B-3K, T700SC-12K and T800HB-6K fibers, their tensile strength and modulus will keep stable and the results have a smaller deviation with their accurate tensile properties when the resin contents of impregnated yarn are more than 30%. However there is a slightly deviation for T700SC-12K impregnated yarn with resin contents of more than 40%, which is attributed to scatter in the quality of specimen, as a result of the larger tows infiltrated uneasily. Resin with lower contents in specimen is not conducive to protecting the fiber tows while testing. Worsely, it maybe becomes the origin of the fracture and induces the tensile fracture.

3.4 The effects of tensile speeds on tensile properties of fibers

The tensile speed is a key parameter when testing the mechanical properties of carbon fibers. If the tensile speed is too slow, it will affect the efficiency of testing. If the tensile speed is too fast, it is easy to cause the deviation of the testing results. So it is reasonable to develop a proper tensile speed in the testing process. In this part, four kind of tensile speeds(1mm/min, 2mm/min, 5mm/min and 10mm/min) can be investigated. Besides as discussed above, resin A is also chosen and the resin contents are kept more than 30%.

Figure 6: The effects of tensile speeds on tensile properties of resin A-impregnated fibers.
(a) Tensile strength. (b) Tensile modulus

In Fig.6, it is obvious that the tensile strength of carbon fibers at a tensile speed of 10mm/min is a little lower than that at 1mm/min, 2mm/min or 5mm/min. The higher tensile speeds can lead to the rapid expand of some defects inside impregnated yarn, at which stress concentration will be produced. And stress concentration cannot be transferred by interface at a higher tensile speed easily causing a sudden fracture. So the higher tensile speeds are not recommended like 10mm/min or higher than it. The lower tensile speeds are virtually no effect on the tensile strength of carbon fibers (T300B-3K and

T800HB-6K). However for T700SC-12K fibers they can be measured accurately at a speed of 5mm/min, but not be measured accurately at 2mm/min, which cannot be interpreted and need be investigated further later. The tensile modulus slightly changes with the different tensile speeds and it is more accurate at a tensile speed of 2mm/min or 5mm/min. Therefore, we recommend the tensile speeds of 2mm/min and 5mm/min when testing.

3.5 The effects of strain ranges on tensile modulus of fibers

According to ASTM D4018-11, the measured materials whose elongation is more than 1.2% are recommended to employ the strain range of 0.1%-0.6% to calculate its tensile modulus. Three kind of strain ranges (0.2%-0.3%, 0.1%-0.4% and 0.1%-0.6%) are designed to acquire the effects on calculating tensile modulus of fibers. Similarly, resin A and two kind of fibers (T300B-3K and T700SC-12K) are adopted.

Figure7: The effects of strain ranges on tensile modulus of resin A-impregnated fibers.

(a) Tensile modulus of T300B-3K. (b) Tensile modulus of T700SC-12K

The modulus of carbon fibers is determined by the slope of the tensile curve at the beginning. However, with understanding carbon fibers further, it becomes pretty popular that relying on the extensometer for the accurate determination of its modulus. As shown in Fig.7, the tensile modulus measured at the strain range of 0.1%-0.6%, a relatively accurate modulus, is closer to the manufacture's recommendation (almost 230GPa), which is consistent with the provisions of the ASTM standard. There are a certain degree of deviations with 230GPa when he strain range of 0.2%-0.3% or 0.1%-0.4% is employed to count the tensile modulus.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The appropriate determination parameters for impregnated yarn were proposed for the tensile tests, which were achieved by a large number of comparative tests. The results showed that resins with high mechanical properties, good wettability, and low viscosity in room temperature could be employed, and the resin content of impregnated yarn should be controlled more than 30%. Furthermore, the tensile speed of 2mm/min and 5mm/min is suitable for the determination of tensile properties of impregnated

yarn. As for the determination of modulus, strain range between 0.1% and 0.6% could be adopted for setting the strain parameters of extensometer. This work has some directing significance in comparing the tensile results with the different test institutions based on the same key parameters.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their gratitude towards the Laboratory of Polymer Matrix Composites, Beihang University, for the support of this research.

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